

Sale of naming rights for eight physical equations

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Abstract: I have eight unnamed physical equations. Now I plan to sell the naming rights for each equation. The minimum price for each equation is 10kg gold. I will check the price every three years and consider whether to sell it. If you are willing to bid 100kg gold, then you can definitely choose an equation and give it a name. The content of this article is valid forever. The content of this article will be effective from 00:01 on October 26, 2021.

Key words: The explanation of universal gravitation, the explanation of the rest mass of the electron, the explanation of the basic charge, the explanation of the mass of the proton.

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The following are eight physical equations without names, that is,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1, \frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(a_0)} = 2\pi(m_e)[\alpha_0](c) , \\ 2, \frac{(e_o)(R_\infty)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)} = (c) , \\ 3, \frac{1}{2}(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2 = \frac{(m_{atom})(c)^2}{2\pi(R_\infty)} , \\ 4, \frac{(e_o)^2(R_\infty)}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)} = \frac{(m_e)(R_\infty)(G_N)}{(K_B)} , \\ 5, 2\pi(\mu_B)(m_e) = (m_e)(R_\infty)^2(G_N) * (m_e)(R_\infty)^2(G_N) , \\ 6, \frac{(m_{atom})(c)^2}{(r_{atom})} = \frac{[\alpha_0](c)(r_e)(2\pi)^4}{(a_0)} , \\ 7, \frac{(e_o)}{2(r_{atom})} = (R_\infty)^3(a_0)^3(2)^3(2\pi)^6, \\ 8, \frac{(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{2(r_e)} = (c)2(r_{atom})(2\pi)^4, \end{array} \right.$$

Where (c) is the Speed of light, (e_o) is the Elementary charge, $[\alpha_0]$ is the Fine structure constant, (R_∞) is the Rydberg constant, (a_0) is the Bohr radius, (m_{atom}) is the Basic atomic mass, (m_e) is the Electron rest mass, (G_N) is the Gravitational constant, (r_e) is the Radius of electron, (r_{am}) is the Radius of proton.

Reference: 1, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4779601>,
2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5059941>,
3, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4518870>.